
Pulpal Inflammation: Harmonizing The Double-Edged Sword

Dr. Niladri Maiti¹, Dr. Alisirbabakuliyev², Dr. Duran Kala³ and Ribwar Fadhil Khalid⁴

¹associate Professor, Department Of Endodontics, Faculty Of Dentistry, Tishk International University, Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

²asst Lecturer, Department Of Endodontics, Faculty Of Dentistry, Tishk International University, Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

³lecturer & Dean, Faculty Of Dentistry, Tishk International University, Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

⁴asst Lecturer, Department Of Oral Diagnosis and Radiology, Faculty Of Dentistry, Tishk International University, Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Corresponding Author Email: Niladri.Maiti@Tiu.Edu.Iq

Issue Details Issue Title: Issue 3

Received: 08 February, 2021

Accepted: 19 March, 2021

Published: 22 May, 2021

Pages: - 1936 – 1942

Copyright © 2020 by author(s) and
Linguistica Antverpiensia

Abstract

The Unique Defensive Response Of Dental Pulp To Any External Stimuli By Inflammation Has Long Been A Mechanism Of Interest For Us. On One Hand, It Marks The Beginning Of Any Dental Pathology Whereas On The Other It Also Marks The Initiation Of Dental Repair And Regeneration. Thus We Have Been Attempting To Better Comprehend The Inflammatory Biomarkers Associated And Also The Most Practical And Reliable Site To Assay The Same. This Review Article Assembles Few Of The Studies Undertaken For Harmonizing This Double Edged Sword And Hence Provide Better Endodontic Therapeutics.

Keywords: Pulpal Inflammation, Biomarkers, Cell Mediators

Introduction

Pulp Is A Unique Richly Innervated And Vascular Soft Tissue Encaged Within Mineralized Hard Tissues Comprising Of Cementum, Enamel And Dentin Thus Making It Extremely Sensitive To Any External Stimuli.^{1,2} Many Factors Including Microbial Ingression By Dental Caries, Chemical Or Mechanical Irritation Caused During Dental Procedures Like Etching, Bonding Or Cavity Preparation, Dentinal Cracks, Trauma From Occlusion Or Orthodontic Tooth Movement Can Initiate The Inflammatory Cascade Within The Pulp.^{3,4,5,6} This Inflammation Has Long Been Associated With Degrading Consequences As Mild As Pain And Root Resorption Due To Neurogenic Inflammation Which Can Transform To Necrosis Including Pyoptosis, Apoptosis And Necrosis And Even Apical Periodontitis In Extreme Form. However, Recently Pulpal Inflammation Has Evidenced Itself To Be A Prerequisite For Any Kind Of Pulp Healing By Contributing To Hard Tissue Remodelling By Recruiting Various Immunocompetent And Regenerative Cells.^{7,8,9} Thus, Making It Extremely Imperative For Us To Have In Depth Knowledge About This Two Edged Sword Of Pulpal Inflammation Enabling Us To Better Modulate Our Diagnosis And Treatment Procedures.

Though Histologic Diagnosis For Pulpal Conditions Has Been The Gold Standard However Its Practical Difficulty Has Compelled Us To Use Clinical Signs And Symptoms For The Same Which Classifies It As Normal, Reversible Pulpitis,

Irreversible Pulpitis And Necrotic.^{10,11,12} Though Histology Can Accurately Reveal The Two Extremes Of Pulpal Inflammation , The Corundum Lies In Effectively Differentiating Between Reversible And Irreversible Pulpitis Wherein Both Clinical And Histological Examinations Have Failed To Accurately Classify Them, Thus Rendering Us With No Accurate Diagnostic Aid. Reversible Pulpitis Has Been Characterized By An Exaggerated Non Lingered Response To Cold Stimulus With Presence Of Liquefaction Or Coagulation Necrosis Surrounding The Irritant With Absence Of Any Bacteria Thus Exhibiting The Potential Of Regeneration Upon Removal Of The Irritant. On The Other Hand, Irreversible Pulpitis Can Show No Pain Or Have An Exaggerated Spontaneous Lingered Response To Cold Stimulus With Display Of Chemotactic Activity By Acute Inflammatory Cells Predominantly Neutrophils Excreting Lysosomal Enzymes Causing Vast Areas Of Pulpal Destruction And Discharge With Presence Of Bacteria Or Its By-Products Hence Exhibiting No Signs Of Regeneration With Pulpectomy Being The Choice Of Treatment.^{13,14,15}

Currently We Routinely Combine Case History Recording, Clinical Examination Along With Radiographic Examination To Diagnose Any Pulpal Condition Wherein Clinical Examination Includes Inspection, Pain On Percussion/Palpation, Pulp Sensitivity To Electric/Thermal Stimuli.^{16,17} A Thorough Literature Review Has Revealed All These Diagnostic Procedures To Be Unreliable In Accurately Diagnosing The Histopathological Status Of Dental Pulp Even Upon Combination. Despite Of The Same No Drastic Evolvement In Any Practical Diagnostic Procedure Has Been Made In The Past Decade Exposing Us To Our Reality Of Still Being Incapable Of Choosing The Best Pulp Treatment Option For Our Patients.

Thus, The Release Of Inflammatory Biomarkers Is Invariably The Classical Sign Of Any Stimulation To Pulp Which Initiates A Vascular Response With Subsequent Changes In Cellular And Mediator Profiles. These Biomarkers Can Be Effectively Quantified To Assess The Pulpal Status And Formulate An Accurate Diagnoses And Treatment Plan.^{18,19} These Biomarkers Can Be Taken From All The Surroundings Whereit Extends Its Biological Products Which Includes Pulpal Blood, Dentinal Fluid, Periapical Fluid And Gingival Crevicular Fluid. These Assays Have Been Obtained Both Directly And Indirectly From Pulp Since Direct Pulpal Blood Or Pulpal Tissue Access Has Been Found To Be Invasive And Not Clinically Feasible. On The Other Hand, Periapical Fluid Access Has Been Used To Elucidate Systemic Inflammation Although Requiring A Direct Invasive Approach. However Even Dentinal Fluid Collection Has Been Found To Be Associated With Its Limitations Of Warranting The Removal Of Old Restoration Or Initial Dentinal Cavity Preparation Along With Complications In Adequate Protein Yielding.^{19,20}

Discussion

In Periodontology, Biomarkers In Saliva And Gingival Crevicular Fluid Like Mmp's 8 And 9 Have Been Routinely Used To Diagnose Periodontal Pockets As They Indicate Soft Tissue Breakdown. As Soft Tissue Breakdown Is A Common Finding In Both Pulpitis And Periodontitis Hence It Can Be Postulated That These Biomarkers Can Also Be Used To Diagnose Pulpitis. However, The Reliability Of The Same Is Yet To Be Confirmed.^{21,22} On The Other Hand Few Studies Assaying Gingival Crevicular Fluid For Diagnosing Pupal Conditions Have Reported Certain Drawbacks Like Inability Of Distinguishing Between Apical Or Marginal Periodontitis Due To Inflammation Being A Non-Specific Innate Immunity Response Even Though It Was Found To Be A Practical Screening Procedure To

Diagnose Apical Periodontal Changes. It Was Postulated That These Errors Could Be Omitted Perhaps By Ensuring A Healthy Periodontium And Specific Metabolite Sequence Exclusive For Pulp That Too Assayed At Specific Sites Only And Eventually Combining It With Other Diagnostic Aids.^{23,24} Moreover, The Belief Of Pupal Mediators Diffusing Via Dentinal And Accessory Canals To Periodontal Ligament And Ultimately The Gingival Crevice In Sufficient Amounts To Be Assayed Has Also Been Questioned.^{25,26}

In Order To Identify The Specific Inflammatory Biomarkers For Diagnosing Pulpal Conditions Explanted Cell Cultures Have Also Been Studied Though Their Reliability Has Been Found To Be Highly Questionable Due To Their Reductionist Nature.^{27,28} On The Other Hand, In Vivo Studies Are Masked By Presence Of Immune Cells, Inhibitory Proteins And Other Individual Host Factors Which May Modulate The Pulpal Immune Response Thus Also Rendering Theminefficient.²⁹never The Less, Clinical Significance Of Identifying And Assaying These Biomarkers Has Been Recognized With An Attempt Of Improving Our Skills On The Same With Few Of Them Being Listed Below.

Invariably,Pulpitis Initiates Inflammatory Reaction Leading To Release Of Certain Mediators Like Tlr Induced Chemotactic Molecules(Interleukin 8, Cxcl-10,Mip Family,Gro,Mcp Family,Rantes,Eotaxin,Ip10 And Others Which Collectively Attempt A Repair.^{30,31,32,33} These Immunocompetent Tlrs Are Expressed By Both Immune And Non-Immune Cells Of Pulp Like Endothelial Cells, Epithelial Cells, Fibroblasts, Neurons, Bacterial Or Viral Microorganism Or Even By Self-Cells During Inflammation.^{34,35}

In A Non-Inflamed Pulp Very Few Immune Cells Are Present In Contrast To An Inflamed Pulp Which Is Extremely Sensitive To Any Bacterial Product Which Leaks Indirectly Through The Dentin And Initiates The Chemotactic Leukocytic Response Along With The Complement System And Lipoxigenase Pathway Of Arachidonic Acid Metabolism.^{36,37}

The Typical Destructive Pulpal Response Has Been Associated With The Release Of Lysosomal Enzymes By These Leukocytes Causing Extensive Tissue Damage Accompanied By The Cleavage Of Elastin And Proteoglycans By Proteases Like Elastase And Mmp's.^{38,39} This Is Also Accompanied By Contraction Of Vascular Smooth Muscles And Cytoskeletal Rearrangement Due To A Hike In Prostaglandins, Cyclic Amp,Cox-2,Cgrp And Neurokinins Which Collectively Cause Vasodilation And Increased Vascular Permeability. Their Action Is Supplemented By The Neuropeptides Like Substance P And Calcitonin Gene Related Peptide Which Are Secreted From Afferent Nerve Endings Causing Spontaneous Pain, Allodynia Or Hyperalgesia.^{40,41} Few Studies Have Substantiated A Simultaneous Increase In Endogenous Opioidsand Sensory Neuropeptides Like Substance P (Sp), Calcitonin Gene-Related Peptide (Cgrp), *B*-Endorphins (*B*-End), And Methionine-Enkephalin (Met-Enk) Resulting In Pain Of Pulpal Origin Even Due To Orthodontic Intrusion.³⁵

These Destructive Effects Are Coupled With The Constructive Effects Of Molecules Like Vegf,Tgf-B And Gm-Csf Which Aid In Proliferation Of Endothelial Cells And Inhibit Vascular Growth Enhancing Differentiation Of Capillaries And Thus Altering The Local Extracellular Matrix. Along With These The Toll Mediated Human Beta Defensins Activate The Host's Innate Immunity Against Any Microbial Invasion By Its Chemotactic Action. Additionally Anti-

Inflammatory Effects Of Various Tissue Inhibitors Of Matrix Proteinases, Sirna And Others Also Contribute In The Same.^{42,43} Toll Like Receptors, C Type Lectin Receptors , Nucleotide Binding Oligomerization Domain Like Receptors, The Retinoic Acid Inducible Gene I Like Receptors And The Aim2 Like Receptors All Collectively Are Pathogen Recognition Receptors Which Aid In Recognizing Pathogen Associated Molecular Patterns And Thus Form An Important Step Of Initiating The Innate Immunity Of An Individual. Their Immunomodulation Mechanism In Pulpal Inflammation Has Been An Interest To Many Authors.³⁵

The Cellular Level Response To Of Pulpal Tissue To Resist The Invading Bacteria Has Been Studied By Various Authors In Which Cytokine Il-8 Has Verified To Be Of Particular Significance In Upregulating The Neutrophils And Also Maintaining The Balance Between The Consequent Degenerative And Reparative Response Amounting To Subsequent Pulpal Healing. Few Studies Have Even Reported The Anti-Inflammatory Effect Of Human Telomerase Derived Peptide Gv 1001 Stimulated By Lipopolysaccharide From P. Gingivalis Thus Proving It To Be Used As A Potential Regenerative Endodontic Therapeutic Agent. Though The Cellular Balance For Optimum Pulp Dentin Regeneration Has Long Been Studied However, Many Studies Have Even Suggested Orthotopic Transplantation Of Dental Pulp Tissue For More Reliable And Clinically Extrapolable Results. Never The Less, As A Consensus The Undesirable Effects Of Pulpal Inflammation Have Now Been Accepted As A Prerequisite Of Pulpal Healing With Both The Components Being Inseparable. This View Has Been Supported By Many Postulating Inflammation Mediated Pulpal Cell Proliferation, Reparative Dentinal Bridge Formulation And Even Initiation Of Mineralization.³⁵ The Mechanism Of Inflammation Has Been Coupled With Immunoregulation Even In Rat Incisors Wherein An Upregulation Of Il6, Il1-B, Tnf-A, Ccl2, Cxcl1, Cxcl2, Mmp9, And Inos Gene Expression Along With Immunoregulatory Cytokine Il 10 Was Observed Following Lps Exposure Thus Highlighting The Importance Of Cellular Balance.⁴⁴

Many Attempts Of Achieving This Balance Are Being Targeted And Aimed To Be Utilized For Effective Endodontic Therapeutics. The High Alkalinity Of Pulp Capping Agents Have Been Contributed In Initiating Pulpitis Leading To Proliferation Of Cells And Subsequent Mineralization Contributing In Odontoblast Like Cells Producing Collagen Type I, Alkaline Phosphatase And Sparc/Osteonectin. Sibling Family Molecules, Matrix Metalloproteinases And Various Nerve And Vascular Mediators Thereafter Collectively Contribute In Reparative Dentinal Bridge Formation By Osteodentin Closing The Pulpal Exposure. Thus Depending Upon The Pulpal Condition A Specific Direction Of Inflammation Can Be Chosen By Giving An Appropriate Capping Agent.⁴⁵since Healthy Dental Pulp Expresses Melatonin And Mt1 And Mt2 Receptors In Odontoblastic And Pulpal Tissue Layer Therefore Its Immunoregulation Has Also Been Studied Upon Exposure To Lps. Wherein Melatonin Has Been Found To Exert Antagonist Effect On Lps Induced Cox-2 And Il-1 B In Pulpal Fibroblasts Thus Suggesting A Promising Immunomodulatory Role Of Melatonin In Therapeutics.⁴⁶ The Use Of Hypoxia Induced Stem Cells From Human Exfoliated Deciduous Teeth To Induce An Environment Conductive For Taking The Pulpal Inflammation Two Edged Sword More Towards The Regeneration Side Has Also Been Suggested By Some Studies Hence Indicating Its Use In Regenerative Endodontics.⁴⁷

Considering The Most Frequent Complication To Be Pulpal Necrosis Following Coronal Restoration Of An Assumed Vital Pulp And Also Frequent Occurring Of Pulpotomy Being Administered To A Tooth Which Could Have Been Preserved Highlights The Necessity Of Current Endodontic Diagnostic Aids To Take Into Account The Extent Of Microbial Infection And The Associated Host Tissue Response.^{48,49}

Conclusion

The Imbalance Between Destructive And Inductive Biomarkers Released By Pulpal Tissue Can Serve As An Efficient Diagnostic And Prognostic Endodontic Tool With The Challenge Being To Develop A Chairside Tool Capable Of Measuring The Same. Thus, This Unique Pulpal Inflammatory Process Continues To Unfold New Mechanisms And Processes And Thus Be A Pivotal Mystery For Us To Master Pulpal Therapeutics.

References

1. Heyeraas K. J., Kvinnsland I. Tissue Pressure And Blood Flow In Pulpal Inflammation. *Proceedings Of The Finnish Dental Society*. 1992;88, Supplement 1:393–401.
2. Van Hassel H. J. Physiology Of The Human Dental Pulp. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology*. 1971;32(1):126–134.
3. Heyeraas K. J., Berggreen E. Interstitial Fluid Pressure In Normal And Inflamed Pulp. *Critical Reviews In Oral Biology And Medicine*. 1999;10(3):328–336.
4. Kim S., Dörscher-Kim J. Hemodynamic Regulation Of The Dental Pulp In A Low Compliance Environment. *Journal Of Endodontics*. 1989;15(9):404–408.
5. Yu C., Abbott P. V. An Overview Of The Dental Pulp: Its Functions And Responses To Injury. *Australian Dental Journal*. 2007;52(4):P. S16.
6. Sen B. H., Piskin B., Demirci T. Observation Of Bacteria And Fungi In Infected Root Canals And Dentinal Tubules By Sem. *Endodontics & Dental Traumatology*. 1995;11(1):6–9.
7. Baik J. E., Ryu Y. H., Han J. Y., Et Al. Lipoteichoic Acid Partially Contributes To The Inflammatory Responses To *Enterococcus Faecalis*. *Journal Of Endodontics*. 2008;34(8):975–982.
8. Choi B.-D., Jeong S.-J., Wang G., Et Al. Temporal Induction Of Secretory Leukocyte Protease Inhibitor (Slpi) In Odontoblasts By Lipopolysaccharide And Wound Infection. *Journal Of Endodontics*. 2009;35(7):997–1002.
9. Love R. M., Jenkinson H. F. Invasion Of Dentinal Tubules By Oral Bacteria. *Critical Reviews In Oral Biology And Medicine*. 2002;13(2):171–183.
10. Levin Lg, Law As, Holland Gr, Abbott Pv, Roda Rs. Identify And Define All Diagnostic Terms For Pulpal Health And Disease States. *J Endod*. 2009;35: 1645–1657.
11. Dummer Pm, Hicks R, Huws D. Clinical Signs And Symptoms In Pulp Disease. *Int Endod J*. 1980;13: 27–35.
12. Seltzer S, Bender Ib, Ziontz M. The Dynamics Of Pulp Inflammation: Correlations Between Diagnostic Data And Actual Histologic Findings In The Pulp. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol*. 1963;16: 846–871 Contd.
13. Ricucci D, Loghin S, Siqueira Jf Jr, Correlation Between Clinical And Histologic Pulp Diagnoses. *J Endod*. 2014;40: 1932–1939.
14. Trowbridge H. Pathogenesis Of Pulpitis Resulting From Dental Caries. *J Endod*. 1981;7: 52–60.

15. Allareddy V, Rampa S, Lee Mk, Allareddy V, Nalliah Rp. Hospital-Based Emergency Department Visits Involving Dental Conditions: Profile And Predictors Of Poor Outcomes And Resource Utilization. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2014;145: 331–337.
16. The Pew Center On The States. A Costly Dental Destination. Pew Children's Dental Campaign 2012. <http://www.pewtrusts.org/~media/assets/2012/01/16/a-costly-dental-destination.pdf>
17. Michaelson P, Holland G. Is Pulpitis Painful. *Int Endod J.* 2002;35: 829–832.
18. Baume R. *Lehrbuch Der Zahnheilkunde.* 1st Ed Leipzig: Arthur Felix; 1877.
19. Mejare Ia, Axelsson S, Davidson T, Frisk F, Hakeberg M, Kvist T, Et Al. Diagnosis Of The Condition Of The Dental Pulp: A Systematic Review. *Int Endod J.* 2012;45: 597–613.
20. Walton Re, Langeland K. Migration Of Materials In The Dental Pulp Of Monkeys. *J Endod.* 1978;4: 167–177.
21. Vongsavan N, Matthews Rw, Matthews B. The Permeability Of Human Dentine In Vitro And In Vivo. *Arch Oral Biol.* 2000;45: 931–935.
22. Mente J, Petrovic J, Gehrig H, Rampf S, Michel A, Schurz A, Et Al. A Prospective Clinical Pilot Study On The Level Of Matrix Metalloproteinase-9 In Dental Pulpal Blood As A Marker For The State Of Inflammation In The Pulp Tissue. *J Endod.* 2016;42: 190–197.
23. Zehnder M, Rechenberg Dk, Bostanci N, Sisman F, Attin T. Comparison Of Vehicles To Collect Dentinal Fluid For Molecular Analysis. *J Dent.* 2014;42: 1027–1032.
24. Rechenberg Dk, Bostanci N, Zehnder M, Belibasakis Gn. Periapical Fluid Rankl And Il-8 Are Differentially Regulated In Pulpitis And Apical Periodontitis. *Cytokine.* 2014;69: 116–119.
25. Avellan Ni, Sorsa T, Tervahartiala T, Forster C, Kempainen P. Experimental Tooth Pain Elevates Substance P And Matrix Metalloproteinase-8 Levels In Human Gingival Crevice Fluid. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2008;66: 18–22.
26. Rechenberg D, Galicia J, Peters O. Biological Markers For Pulpal Inflammation: A Systematic Review. *Plos One.* 2016;11(11):E0167289.
27. Botero Tm, Shelburne Ce, Holland Gr, Hanks Ct, Nor Je. Tlr4 Mediates Lps-Induced Vegf Expression In Odontoblasts. *J Endod.* 2006;32: 951–955.
28. Carrouel F, Staquet Mj, Keller Jf, Baudouin C, Msika P, Bleicher F, Et Al. Lipopolysaccharide-Binding Protein Inhibits Toll-Like Receptor 2 Activation By Lipoteichoic Acid In Human Odontoblast-Like Cells. *J Endod.* 2013;39: 1008–1014.
29. Farges Jc, Carrouel F, Keller Jf, Baudouin C, Msika P, Bleicher F, Et Al. Cytokine Production By Human Odontoblast-Like Cells Upon Toll-Like Receptor-2 Engagement. *Immunobiology.* 2011;216: 513–517.
30. Bhattacharyya S, Kelley K, Melichian Ds, Tamaki Z, Fang F, Su Y, Et Al. Toll-Like Receptor 4 Signaling Augments Transforming Growth Factor-Beta Responses: A Novel Mechanism For Maintaining And Amplifying Fibrosis In Scleroderma. *Am J Pathol.* 2013;182: 192–205.
31. Villalba M, Hott M, Martin C, Aguila B, Valdivia S, Quezada C, Et Al. Herpes Simplex Virus Type 1 Induces Simultaneous Activation Of Toll-Like Receptors 2 And 4 And Expression Of The Endogenous Ligand Serum Amyloid A In Astrocytes. *Med Microbiol Immunol.* 2012;201: 371–379.
32. Shi B, Huang Q, Tak Pp, Vervoordeldonk Mj, Huang Cc, Dorfleutner A, Et Al. Snapin: An Endogenous Toll-Like Receptor Ligand In Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2012;71: 1411–1417.

-
33. Goh Fg, Piccinini Am, Krausgruber T, Udalova Ia, Midwood Ks. Transcriptional Regulation Of The Endogenous Danger Signal Tenascin-C: A Novel Autocrine Loop In Inflammation. *J Immunol.* 2010;184: 2655–2662.
34. Merline R, Moreth K, Beckmann J, Nastase Mv, Zeng-Brouwers J, Tralhao Jg, Et Al. Signaling By The Matrix Proteoglycan Decorin Controls Inflammation And Cancer Through Pdcd4 And Microrna-21. *Sci Signal.* 2011;4: Ra75 10.1126/Scisignal.2001868
35. Park S, Ye L, Love R, Farges J, Yumoto H. Inflammation Of The Dental Pulp. *Mediators Of Inflammation.* 2015;2015:1-2.
36. Izumi T, Kobayashi I, Okamura K, Sakai H. Immunohistochemical Study On The Immunocompetent Cells Of The Pulp In Human Non-Carious And Carious Teeth. *Arch Oral Biol.* 1995;40: 609–614.
37. Moreland Lw. *Rheumatology And Immunology Therapy.* 1st Ed Springer; Berlin Heidelberg New York; 2004.
38. Caviedes-Bucheli J, Munoz Hr, Azuero-Holguin Mm, Ulate E. Neuropeptides In Dental Pulp: The Silent Protagonists. *J Endod.* 2008;34: 773–788.
39. Byers Mr. Effects Of Inflammation On Dental Sensory Nerves And Vice Versa. *Proc Finn Dent Soc.* 1992;88 Suppl 1: 499–506.
40. Nakanishi T, Takahashi K, Hosokawa Y, Adachi T, Nakae H, Matsuo T. Expression Of Macrophage Inflammatory Protein 3alpha In Human Inflamed Dental Pulp Tissue. *J Endod.* 2005;31: 84–87.
41. Gusman H, Santana Rb, Zehnder M. Matrix Metalloproteinase Levels And Gelatinolytic Activity In Clinically Healthy And Inflamed Human Dental Pulp. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2002;110: 353–357.
42. Sunderkotter C, Steinbrink K, Goebeler M, Bhardwaj R, Sorg C. Macrophages And Angiogenesis. *Journal Of Leukocyte Biology.* 1994;55: 410–422.
43. Galicia Jc, Naqvi Ar, Ko Cc, Nares S, Khan Aa. Mirna-181a Regulates Toll-Like Receptor Agonist-Induced Inflammatory Response In Human Fibroblasts. *Genes Immun.* 2014;15: 333–337.
44. Renard E, Gaudin A, Bienvenu G, Amiaud J, Farges J, Cuturi M Et Al. Immune Cells And Molecular Networks In Experimentally Induced Pulpitis. *Journal Of Dental Research.* 2015;95(2):196-205.
45. Goldberg M, Njeh A, Uzunoglu E. Is Pulp Inflammation A Prerequisite For Pulp Healing And Regeneration?. *Mediators Of Inflammation.* 2015;2015:1-11.
46. . Kantrong N, Jit-Armart P, Arayatrakoolkit U. Melatonin Antagonizes Lipopolysaccharide-Induced Pulpal Fibroblast Responses. *Bmc Oral Health.* 2020;20(1).
47. Colombo J, Jia S, D'souza R. Modeling Hypoxia Induced Factors To Treat Pulpal Inflammation And Drive Regeneration. *Journal Of Endodontics.* 2020;46(9):S19-S25.
48. Levin Lg, Law As, Holland Gr, Abbott Pv, Roda Rs. Identify And Define All Diagnostic Terms For Pulpal Health And Disease States. *J Endod.* 2009;35: 1645–1657.
49. Simon S, Perard M, Zanini M, Smith Aj, Charpentier E, Djole Sx, Et Al. Should Pulp Chamber Pulpotomy Be Seen As A Permanent Treatment? Some Preliminary Thoughts. *Int Endod J.* 2013;46: 79–87.